

Chemisorption of Oxygen by Graphon on Various Treatments

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Chemisorption of oxygen on Graphon, a highly graphitised carbon black, on treatment with oxygen (400°), ozone (in water and carbon tetrachloride at ordinary temperature), hot concentrated nitric acid and oxidising solutions of ceric sulphate, potassium persulphate and hydrogen peroxide are reported. The surface covered by the oxygen, on various treatments, varies between 2.5 and 13.8 m²/g., before pre-activation and between 6.3 and 21.9 m²/g., after pre-activation of Graphon to 17.2 per cent burn-off. The B.E.T. (nitrogen) surface area of Graphon increases from 76 m² to 98 m²/g., on activation; the maximum surface coverage by oxygen, therefore, corresponds to about 18 per cent before and 22 per cent after the burn-off. The chemisorbed oxygen comes off largely as carbon dioxide and to a much smaller extent as carbon monoxide. The presence of oxygen imparts acidity to the surface which, however, is not equivalent to the amount of CO₂-complex formed. The presence of oxygen imparts hydrophilicity to the surface although it does not alter benzophilicity of the surface to any noticeable extent.

OXOGEN chemisorption studies on Graphon, a highly graphitised carbon black considered to have a clean surface, before and after pre-activation at different burn-offs, in the temperature range 300°-625°, at low oxygen pressures¹⁻³ as well as at 25° under oxygen pressure range of 0.7 millitorr to 760 torr⁴ and also at a constant pressure of 100 millitorr in the temperature range⁵-78° to 160° have been reported by Walker and coworkers. The oxygen chemisorbed at low pressures upto 0.5 torr in the temperature range 300°-625° has been found to correspond to surface coverage of only 2-3 per cent of the B.E.T. area²⁻³. This suggested that carbon atoms located at the edges of the basal planes only were active in the process. It would be of interest to know the extent to which the surface would be covered by oxygen if Graphon is given more extensive oxidation treatments and the form in which the oxygen would be desorbed on evacuation at high temperatures and the effect which it would have on acidity and hydrophilicity of the Graphon surface.

Experimental

Graphon, supplied by Cabot Corporation, Boston, Mass., through the courtesy of Dr. Rivin, was used before as well as after burn-off in oxygen⁶ at 625° to the extent of 17.2 per cent, for the present investigations. The samples were outgassed at 950° and kept stored in bottles flushed with nitrogen till required for use. The B.E.T. surface area (nitrogen) of Graphon was found to be 76 m²/g., in agreement with the reports of previous workers. It increased to 98 m²/g. as a result of 17.2 per cent burn-off. The following oxidation treatments were given:

1. *Treatment in oxygen at 400°*: Graphon (5 g.) was taken in a rotating pyrex tube of 3/4" bore which was heated in a silica tube furnace at 400° which has been shown⁷ to be the optimum

temperature for maximum fixation of oxygen by carbons. Dry oxygen of 99.6 per cent purity was led over @ 2 l/hr for 6 hrs. The material was allowed to cool in oxygen and then transferred to stoppered bottles flushed with nitrogen.

2. *Treatment with ozone in aqueous and carbon tetrachloride solutions*: Graphon (5 g) was suspended in water or carbon tetrachloride (150 ml) in a 250 ml standard tapered Erlenmeyer flask and ozonised oxygen (~2.3 per cent ozone) was led through the suspension⁸ for 12 hrs. The suspension was kept stirred using a magnetic stirrer.
3. *Treatment with ceric sulphate*: Graphon (1 g) was mixed with 200 ml of 0.1N ceric sulphate solution in 2N H₂SO₄. The suspension was shaken for 48 hrs and then filtered and the residue washed to free it of sulphate ions.
4. *Treatment with nitric acid*: Graphon (5 g) was mixed with 150 ml of pure nitric acid and heated over a low bunsen flame till the volume was reduced⁹ to 10 ml. The contents were cooled, filtered and the residue washed exhaustively with water.
5. *Treatment with acidified K₂S₂O₈ and aqueous H₂O₂*: Graphon (1 g) was mixed with 200 ml of nearly saturated solution of K₂S₂O₈ in 1M H₂SO₄ or 100 ml of H₂O₂ solution¹⁰. The suspension in either case was shaken for 24 hrs and then filtered and washed.

The oxidised samples dried at 150° in an air oven, were outgassed (0.5 g portion) in a resistance tube furnace, the temperature of which was allowed to rise gradually. The gas evolved was pumped out continuously and analysed for carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide in the manner described before⁷.

Base adsorption capacity was determined by titrating against aqueous barium hydroxide¹⁰ and surface unsaturation by irreversible fixation of bromine¹¹, as described earlier.

Results and Discussions

The amounts of oxygen chemisorbed by Graphon on various treatments and evolved as carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide on outgassing at 1000° are recorded in Table 1. The extent of chemisorption as well as the pattern of disposition of the oxygen is seen to vary with the nature of the treatment. Thus treatment with ceric sulphate solution results in maximum chemisorption of oxygen while that with hot concentrated nitric acid gives the next highest value. Treatments with ozone, in water and carbon tetrachloride solutions, at ordinary temperatures, give lower values which, however, are appreciably higher than the value obtained on treatment with oxygen gas at the optimum temperature of 400°. The treatments with solutions of hydrogen peroxide and potassium persulphate give relatively lower values in the decreasing order of their mention. The extent of chemisorption increases, in each case, when Graphon is subjected to pre-activation in oxygen to the extent of 17.2 per cent burn-off, presumably due to generation of more active sites during the process.

TABLE I—CHEMISORPTION OF OXYGEN BY GRAPHON ON VARIOUS TREATMENTS

Description of the treatment	Oxygen evolved on outgassing at 1000°C as (g./100 g.)			Total area occupied by oxygen (m ² /g)	% area covered by oxygen
	CO ₂	CO	Total		
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
<i>Before any treatment</i>	(a) nil (b) nil	nil nil	nil nil	nil nil	nil nil
<i>After treatment with</i>					
Ceric sulphate	(a) 0.35 (b) 0.56	0.090 0.140	0.440 0.700	13.75 21.88	18.09 22.32
HNO ₃ (100%)	(a) 0.24 (b) 0.30	0.036 0.114	0.276 0.414	8.62 12.94	11.34 13.20
Ozone in water	(a) 0.16 (b) 0.27	0.020 0.105	0.180 0.375	5.62 11.72	7.39 11.96
Ozone in CCl ₄	(a) 0.16 (b) —	0.040 —	0.200 —	6.25 —	8.22 —
O ₂ at 400°C	(a) 0.08 (b) 0.24	0.072 0.090	0.152 0.330	4.75 10.31	6.25 10.52
aq. H ₂ O ₂	(a) 0.12 (b) 0.16	0.030 0.043	0.150 0.203	4.69 6.34	6.17 6.47
K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	(a) 0.08 (b) —	nil —	0.080 —	2.50 —	3.29 —

(a) = Before burn-off, (b) = After 17.2% burn-off.

A major portion of the combined oxygen is seen to come off as carbon dioxide, i.e., it gives rise to what is referred to in the literature, as CO₂-complex. The CO-complex is formed in appreciable measures only when Graphon is treated with ceric sulphate or hot concentrated nitric acid. It may be noted that Tucker and Mulchay¹² showed the formation of CO-complex to be much higher than that of CO₂-complex when they treated their graphitised carbon blacks in oxygen at 550°. This appears to be due to the fact that CO₂-complex, being much less stable than CO-complex, gets eliminated in appreciable amounts as the temperature is raised⁷ beyond 400°.

Since Graphon is supposed to have a highly graphitised structure, chemisorption is considered to occur only on edge carbon atoms lying in the basal plane²⁻³. Assuming each such carbon atom to occupy an area of 8.3 Å² and one oxygen atom to be fixed per active carbon atom³, it can be shown that the total area covered by oxygen in the various oxidation treatments is as given in Table 1 (column 5). It is seen that on the basis of these calculations, the area of Graphon covered by oxygen varies from 2.5 to 13.8 m²/g. before the burn-off and from 6.3 to 21.9 m²/g. after the burn-off, depending upon the nature of the oxidation treatment given. Since the total (B.E.T.) area of Graphon is 76 m² and 98 m²/g., before and after the burn-off, it is evident that maximum surface coverage by oxygen even on such extensive oxidation treatments, as that with ceric sulphate, corresponds to only about 18.09 per cent before and 22.32 per cent after the burn-off. It may be noted that Lussow, Vastola and Walker³ on treating a sample of Graphon, after 19.9 per cent burn-off, with oxygen gas at 300° reported coverage of 5.6 m²/g., which compares with the value of 10.3 m² obtained by us on treatment of our sample (17.2 per cent burn-off) with oxygen at 400°.

The percentage coverages of the surface given in the last column of Table 1 suggest that Graphon is far less susceptible to chemisorption of oxygen than most of the non graphitised carbon blacks in which the percentage coverage has been shown to be very high even under less extensive oxidation treatments¹³.

Since a major portion of the combined oxygen is seen to be present as CO₂-complex, it was thought of interest to see how far it imparts acidic character to the surface. The amounts of barium hydroxide neutralised by Graphon, before and after various treatments, are recorded in Table 2. The amounts of carbon dioxide evolved from the various samples, expressed in similar units, are also included in the Table. It is seen that in a number of cases, the CO₂-complex formed is almost entirely acidic in nature. The non-acidic CO₂-complex, taken as difference between the amount of carbon dioxide evolved and barium hydroxide neutralised, where more than 2 per cent¹⁰, is seen to be formed in small amounts only in case of treatments given with ozone in water, aqueous, hydrogen peroxide and nitric acid. Since this complex is known to be formed through fixation of oxygen at the unsaturated sites¹⁰,

it is interesting to note that bromine value, taken as a measure of surface unsaturation, which was 20 and

of Pierce and Smith¹⁴ that sorption of water on carbons contains oxygen takes place through formation of clusters at the sites covered by oxygen and that these clusters grow in size as sorption increases at rising vapour pressures.

TABLE 2—NATURE OF CO₂-COMPLEX FORMED ON CHEMISORPTION OF OXYGEN BY GRAPHON

Description of the treatment	Total CO ₂ -complex (me/100g)	Ba(OH) ₂ value ≡ acidic CO ₂ -complex (me/100g)	Non-acidic CO ₂ -complex (me/100g)	Bromine value (me/100g)	
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	
Before any treatment	(a)	nil	nil	20	
	(b)	nil	nil	36	
After treatment with					
Ceric sulphate	(a)	22	21.7	nil	18
	(b)	35	35.3	nil	35
HNO ₃ (100%)	(a)	15	5	10	11
	(b)	18.8	19	nil	32
Ozone in water	(a)	10	nil	10	12
	(b)	17	1.5	15.5	17
Ozone in CCl ₄	(a)	10	10	nil	21
	(b)	—	—	—	—
O ₂ at 400°C	(a)	5	5	nil	18
	(b)	15	14.8	nil	34
aq. H ₂ O ₂	(a)	7.5	2.5	5	13
	(b)	10	10	nil	32
K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	(a)	5	5	nil	20
	(b)	—	—	—	—

(a) = Before burn-off, (b) = After 17.2% burn-off.

36 milliequivalents/100 g. before and after the burn-off, respectively, decreases by an amount almost equivalent to that of non acidic complex formed. It is not possible, however, at this stage, to offer any explanation why certain treatments give rise to both acidic and non acidic CO₂-complexes while others give rise only to the acidic complex.

The water isotherms on Graphon, before and after any treatment, as well as after treatments with ceric sulphate and nitric acid are plotted in Fig. 1. It is interesting to note that although Graphon, as such, is extremely hydrophobic as it does not take up any noticeable amount of water vapour even at vapour pressures close to saturation vapour pressure, becomes fairly hydrophilic and takes up increasing amounts of water vapour at increasing relative vapour pressures after chemisorption of oxygen. The isotherm on the oxygenated samples are of type II indicating formation of multilayers. However, it can be shown by simple calculations that the number of statistical layers formed even at a pressure close to saturation vapour pressure (i.e., $p/p_0 = 0.94$) does not exceed 1 (taking area of Graphon as 76 m²/g and molecular area of water as 10.6 Å²). It appears, therefore, that multilayers are formed only around the sites covered by oxygen. This supports the view

Fig. 1. Benzene and water vapour adsorption isotherms (35°) on Graphon before and after oxidation.

Carbon blacks, both graphitised¹⁵ and non graphitised¹⁶, are known to adsorb appreciable amounts of benzene vapour. The data, in fact, have been used for calculating surface area¹⁷⁻¹⁸ and micropore volume¹⁹ of the carbons. The benzene isotherm included in Fig. 1 shows that Graphon also takes up appreciable amounts of benzene at all relative vapour pressures. The isotherm is of type II and the knee of the graph is seen to correspond to the amount (22 mg/g) which is just enough to form a monolayer. The amount adsorbed at $p/p_0 = 0.87$ corresponds roughly to formation of 5 statistical layers.

Since the presence of combined oxygen imparts hydrophilicity to the surface, as discussed above, it was considered likely that it might affect adversely the adsorbability of benzene. The isotherm on one of the oxygenated samples, included in Fig. 1, however, does not show any significant alteration. This behaviour may be explained on the basis of a recent report from these laboratories²⁰ that while the acidic CO₂-complex suppresses the sorption of benzene, the non-acidic complex has no such effect and the CO-complex, constituted by quinonic oxygen, promotes the sorption of benzene. It appears that in the present case the adverse effect of the acidic complex is more or less compensated by the promotional effect of quinonic oxygen.

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